

Calculation of Activation Energy of Self-diffusion in Some Solid Metals

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A simple method for calculating activation energy of self-diffusion (Q) in some solid metals, utilising the total binding energy of the metal as calculated from Pauling's concept of the metallic valency, has been proposed. The values of Q , estimated for different metals, have been compared with the available experimental data.

As against the vaporisation-diffusion concept of atoms in solids, originated by Eyring and co-workers¹, melting-diffusion concept has been favoured in recent years²⁻⁵. Essential correctness of Eyring's concept of self-diffusion was emphasised in a note⁶. It is desirable to make an attempt at the quantitative calculation of the energy of activation, Q , to lend support to the ideas contained in the note⁶. It may be assumed that self-diffusion in metals occurs by hole-mechanism⁷⁻¹⁰.

The quantum-mechanical calculation of Q is very involved and almost impossible to be carried out in most cases; the only case treated so far is that of copper⁶. Attempts to calculate Q are very few (Frenkel, p. 34)⁷. The alternative method to be presented here is much easier and general and depends on the binding-energy distribution among metal atoms. The disadvantage of its being less sophisticated and rigorous may be ignored in view of its easy nature.

Calculation of ' Q '

The total binding energy $-U_0$ of a metal¹¹ given by

$$-U_0^* = I \times v + S \quad \dots (1)$$

' I ' being the first ionisation potential, ' v ', Pauling's metallic valency, and ' S ', the latent heat of sublimation of the metal concerned, may be assumed to be due to metallic bonds

1. *Ann. Rev. Phys. Chem.*, 1955, 6, 132.
2. Nachtrieb, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1962, 20, 1185.
3. Van Liempt, *Z. Physik*, 1935, 96, 534; *Z. anorg. allgem. Chem.*, 1931, 195, 3.
4. Braune, *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1924, 110, 147.
5. Dienes, *J. Appl. Phys.*, 1950, 21, 1160.
6. Gopal, *Z. anorg. allgem. Chem.*, 1957, 293, 53.
7. Jost, "Diffusion", Academic Press, Inc., 1955, p. 135 ff; Frenkel, "Kinetic Theory of Liquids", Clarendon Press, 1946, p. 28.
8. Huntington and Seitz, *Phys. Rev.*, 1942, 61, 315.
9. *Idem, ibid.*, 1940, 58, 209; 1942, 61, 325.
10. Paneth, *ibid.*, 1950, 80, 708.
11. Gopal and Husain, *this Journal*, 1962, 39, 827.

between the central atom and its 'Z' neighbours, ignoring the effect of more distant atoms. Therefore the contribution to the binding energy of the central atom due to any of its 'Z' neighbours is given by

$$- \left\{ \frac{I \times v + S}{Z} \right\} e.V.$$

Now if one of the surrounding atoms is replaced by a vacancy, the binding electron cloud around the central atom will be only one-half dense on the side of vacancy, i.e., the bond between the central atom and the vacancy will be only one-half strong as compared to the normal bond. This will reduce the binding energy of the central atomic core, for displacements in the direction of vacancy, to one-half of the normal binding energy¹² per neighbour. Consequently, the central atom with vibrational energy $\gg$ one-half of the normal binding energy per neighbour will be in a position to cross the electron-cloud potential barrier in the direction of vacancy, i.e., an atom situated by the side of a vacancy and possessing vibrational energy $\gg$

$$\left\{ \frac{I \times v + S}{2Z} \right\} e.V$$

per g. atom can migrate into the vacancy.

The situation in the body of the metal is not so simple, as visualised above, due to presence of other atoms around the vacancy. The ideal position for such a concept is the layer of atoms just below the atomic surface layer. If an atom on the surface acquires sufficient energy and sublimates, leaving a vacancy in the top layer, the atom next to it in the next lower layer will move into this vacant place in the surface layer when it acquires the required energy. This is made excellently clear from the Figs. 3-5 illustrated by Dekker¹² to which reference can be made. It can be clearly seen from those figures that the energy required for the movement of atoms in the bulk-body of the metal is much less since its movement deep in the inside involves only the migration energy and no hole-formation energy. Thus the energy of activation of self diffusion, Q , can be written as:

$$\left. \begin{aligned} Q &= \left\{ \frac{I \times v + S}{2Z} \right\} e.V. \text{-per g. atom} \\ &= \left\{ \frac{I \times v + S}{2Z} \right\} \times 23 \text{ kcal. per g. atom} \end{aligned} \right\} (2)$$

12. Dekker, "Solid State Physics", Prentice Hall, Inc., N. J., 1958, p. 68.

* $-U_0$ has been called "lattice energy" by us¹¹. The use of the term "lattice energy" may be objected to because of the use of Pauling's metallic valency 'v' in the place of usual chemical valency. The use of this term is justified on the ground that the total number of electrons taking part in the binding of the metals, other than alkali and alkaline earths, is given by 'v', the Pauling valency, and not by the number of chemical valency electrons.

** "Introduction of a vacancy or a hole makes the lattice imperfect and in an imperfect crystal the atoms neighbouring a vacancy will have vibrational frequency smaller than the normal frequency ν_0 because the restoring forces are reduced, particularly along the direction of the line joining the atom and the vacancy" (quoted from Dekker's "Solid State Physics", ref. 12, p. 65). It appears most reasonable to assume that the binding force in this direction is reduced to one-half of the normal value.

The values of Q , calculated from equation (2), along with those obtained experimentally and from the empirical expression $Q=33T_m$ (T_m being the absolute melting point of the metal concerned) are recorded in Table I in a few cases.

TABLE I

Metal.	Metallic valency† 'v' [Pauling]	Nearest neighbours 'Z'	Ionisation potential 'I' (in e. V.)	Heat of sublimation 'S' (in e. V.)	Q (cal./g. atom)		(e.V. × 23000) Expt*,
					Eq (2).	33 T_m .	
Na	1	8	5.12	1.12	9000	11804	10450
Ag	6	12	7.54	2.95	46300	39600	45900
Cu	6	12	7.69	3.52	47700	43600	52000
Au	6	12	9.20	4.00	56700	42800	58000
Fe	6	8	7.83	4.16	73580	58000	77000 (49000)
Co	6	12	7.81	3.09	49000	56000	61000
W**	6	8	8.00	8.80	81700	113400	140000
Zn†	3	12	9.34	1.17	29200	21000	30000 (20000)
Pb†	3	12	7.39	2.04	242000	19000	27900

† These values are round numbers in some cases.

** See the text for the low value of Q .

† Metallic valency has been taken to be 3 instead of 4.5, as given by Pauling, to take into account asymmetry of arrangement of 12 neighbours. This is expected to produce an over-all reduction in the binding energy.

* From Jost, Ref. 7, pp. 234-39.

A critical examination of Table I shows that equation (2) provides a reasonable guess for Q . The predicted values are in no way less satisfactory than those obtained from other empirical relations. Calculated values appear to be slightly lower than the experimental ones, most probably due to omission of the interaction of the diffusing atom and the next neighbours. The cause of rather a low value of Q in tungsten is not clear, but the modified value of $-U_0$ for tungsten¹¹ gives Q as 125000 to 137500 cal. which agrees very well with the experimental value.

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